

VIBHORE JAIN

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Assistant Professor
Department of Computer Science and Engg.
Bhilai Institute of Technology, Durg C.G

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- Experience in teaching different subject under the domain of Computer Science Engineering under different domains like networking, algorithms, software development, testing, and other different trending research areas including Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence.
- Strong Experience of Software Development lifecycle (SDLC), Use Case Analysis, and User Acceptance Testing (UAT).
- Has client-facing skills and ability to work independently and efficiently, managing people, processes, timelines and expectations

RELEVANT SKILLS

Technical Skills

- **Language:** C++, Java, JSP, Servlets, JavaScript, Python (beginner)
- **Operating System:** Windows 8, 10, 11, Ubuntu
- **DBMS:** Oracle 21c, Nodejs, MySQL, Navicat
- **Frameworks** React, Spring, Hibernate

Area of Interest Software Engineering Project Management, Cryptography, Computer Networks

EDUCATION

PhD , Computer Science	MATS University, Raipur	2024- Present
M Tech , Computer Networks	Chhattisgarh Swami Vivekananda Technical University, Durg	2016-2018
MS(c) , Computer Science	University of New Brunswick, Fredericton, Canada	2014-2016
BE , Computer Science and Engineering	Chhattisgarh Swami Vivekananda Technical University, Durg	2009- 2013

WORK EXPERIENCE

Teaching Faculty, Bhilai Institute of Technology Durg
Assistant Professor, CSE Department

July 2021–Present

- Experience with teaching different subject pertaining to field of Computer Science and Engineering.
- Responsible for grading the tests and preparing assignments for students.
- Responsible for keeping a track record of student performance and make necessary arrangements for students who are lagging behind.
- Responsible for keeping records of marks scored by each student and keeping a track on attendance of all students.

Software Developer, Diaspark Inc , Indore

Nov 2013- May 2014

Junior Software Engineer, Inter

- Worked as software developer trainee on technologies including JSP, Servlet, Hibernate.
- Worked on project Care4Today.
- Hands on experience on SQL , Navicat server

Teaching Assistant, Swati Jain Academy, Indore

May 2013-Nov 2013

GRE Scholar cum trainer

- Took classes for GRE/GMAT/SAT
- Responsible for taking classes of students of batch size 40
- Responsible for grading the assignments of students

PROJECTS UNDERTAKEN

Project 1: Sentiment Analysis of Tweets

- Tweets were collected for few days which were analysed.
- Sentiment Analysis of tweets was done by different techniques.
- Score obtained about sentiments of tweets were then analysed and accuracy and limitation of each tool is compared.

Project 2: Active City Administration

- Designed for creating an interface between user and municipal authorities.
- Front end of project was designed using JSP, Servlet
- Backend was developed using Oracle.

Project 3: Election Voting System using Block Chain

- Guided this project on block chain
- Voter registers themselves while giving vote using unique id.
- Unique id is use to create a transaction block using block chain.
- After casting successful vote block is created with unique transaction id and process goes on.
- Met mask was use for transaction.
- Ethereum currency was used for block chain.

Project 4: Online Shopping Mall

- This project was based on online shopping site.
- Designed project for one stop solution for all brands electronic goods.
- Front end was designed using PHP.
- Back end was designed using My SQL.

Project 5: Movie Details Portal

- This is a mini project made under my supervision.
- List of movies poster thumbnail were created.
- Each thumbnail is connected to its movie description page present over internet.
- Front end was created using React JS
- Backend was developed using Node JS.

VOLUNTEER EXPERIENCE

National Social Service

- Volunteered in Environment Awareness Camp and AIDS Awareness camps to spread knowledge about disease.
- Organized Blood donation camps and promoted people for the cause.

Microsoft Dream Spark Yatra

- Participated in technology awareness camp organized by Microsoft.

- Spread awareness about various technologies available in market.

Help Age India

- Worked actively for NGO Help Age India.
- Collected donations for underprivileged children.
- Volunteer in camps organized by Help Age India.

College Level Events

- One of the organizing members of OPIN HACK organized at BIT Durg.
- Organizing committee member of OJAS 2023 cultural fest at BIT Durg.
- Faculty member of ISCA at BIT Durg
- Active member of college annual magazine committee.

AWARDS & CERTIFICATION

- ISTQB Foundation level tester certification.
- OCJP certified Java Programmer.
- Winner of President Award for National Level Essay Writing.
- Winner of MBD State Level Quiz Competition.

FDP&WORKSHOPS

- Attended one day workshop on “Copyright filing for research work”.
- Attended one week National FDP on Generative AI organized by Pantech e learning.
- Attended FDP on Generative AO and NLP organized by GH Rasoni College of Engineering, Nagpur.
- Attended FDP on Business Analytics and Tools organized by RFI, Indore Chapter.

PUBLICATIONS

- Published a paper titled “Statistical Relational Learning” in IJCMS Issue 12 Vol. 9, September 2017.
- Published a paper titled “A Brief Survey and Findings on Trending Issues in Social Media: Sentiment Analysis Approach in IJSRD Issue 1 Vol. 6 March 2018.
- Published a paper titled “Comparative Study of Sentiment Analysis on trending issues on Social Media” in IJAMTES Issue 3 Vol. 8 March 2018.
- Published a paper titled “Sentiment Analysis: An Introductory Approach for Understanding views on Trending Issues in Social Media” in IJRTI Issue 4, Vol. 3, April 2018.
- Published a paper titled “Tools for Comparative study of Sentiment Analysis of Trending Issues on Social Media: A Comparative Study” in IJACEN May 2018.

CONFERENCES

- Presented paper titled “Statistical Relational Learning” at International Conference on Science Technology and Management held at IETE Bangalore in September 2017.
- Presented paper titled “Comparative Study of Sentiment Analysis on trending issues on Social Media” at National Conference BITCON 18, held at BIT Durg in February 2018.
- Presented paper titled “Tools for Comparative study of Sentiment Analysis of Trending Issues on Social Media: A Comparative Study” at International Conference on Big Data Computer Science and Information Technology – ICBDCSIT 2018 held at Pune in May 2018.
- Presented paper titled “Destroke” at International Conference on Contemporary Research, Innovations and Trends in Engineering Applied Science Management and Humanities 2023 in online mode.
- Presented paper titled “A new era demand for women safety: IoT” at International Conference on Contemporary Research, Innovations and Trends in Engineering Applied Science Management and Humanities 2023 in online mode.

